

Supplemental Material for: Additive-enhanced hydrogen- and hydroxide-based magneto-ionic control in Ni films

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Figure S1. Chemical composition of the Ni film obtained by AES depth profiling as a function of sputtering time t , with a sputtering rate of 6 nm/min referenced on SiO_2 on Si. The thickness of the native NiO_x layer is about 5 nm.

Supplementary Note to Figure S1. For Auger electron spectroscopy (AES) measurements, a JEOL JAMP 9500 F (Tokyo, Japan) field emission microscope equipped with a hemispherical analyzer running in the constant retarding ratio mode with an electron beam of 10 keV and 10 nA was used. The depth profiling was performed with Ar^+ ions of 1 keV, resulting in a sputtering rate of 6 nm/min referenced on SiO_2 on Si. The sputtering scan size is approximately $1 \times 1 \text{ mm}^2$. The chemical composition is measured in "spot-mode" on different positions with a spot size of approximately $1.5 \times 1.5 \text{ }\mu\text{m}^2$.

AES combined with sputter depth profiling shows that the oxygen concentrates in the surface layer. The thickness of this nickel oxide surface layer is about 5 nm (assuming similar sputtering rates for Si and Ni), which is as expected for room temperature native oxidation of polycrystalline Ni.¹ The oxygen content in the film volume beyond the nickel surface is less than 2 %. With this low oxygen content, significant oxygen-based magneto-ionic effects, as, e.g. previously reported for a 100 nm-thick polycrystalline Co_3O_4 film,² can be ruled out for the film volume.

Figure S2. Scheme of the electrochemical cell geometry for (a) in situ SQUID magnetometry and (b) in situ MOKE magnetometry. In both cells the electrodeposited Ni film is contacted as working electrode (WE) via the Au layer on the SiO_x/Si wafer. The voltage is applied versus a reference electrode (RE). Current flows through a separate counter electrode (CE). Pt wires are used for both auxiliary electrodes (RE and CE).

Figure S3. Magnetic moment m as a function of magnetic field $\mu_0 H$ in a hysteresis loop for a Ni-film recorded in a field range between -30 and 30 mT at 300 K using SQUID magnetometry. A coercivity of $\mu_0 H_C = 8.5 \text{ mT}$ was obtained for the Ni-film, in good agreement with values from MOKE magnetometry. All subsequent *in situ* SQUID measurements were performed at a field of 0.5 T, where the Ni samples are in a saturated state.

Figure S4. Variation of magnetic saturation moment m_s and applied potential U as a function of time t during voltage cycling in 0.5 M KOH electrolyte as obtained by *in situ* SQUID magnetometry. The second cycle (starting at $t = 50$ min) is shown in an alternative representation as a voltammogram (current vs. potential) in Fig. 1c in the main text.

Figure S5. *In situ* Raman spectra of nickel films **a** in 0.5 M KOH electrolyte solution and **b** in 0.5 M KOH electrolyte solution with thiourea additive. The curves are shifted along the vertical axis to facilitate comparison. In both graphs, the Raman spectrum of the *ex situ* state (a Ni film measured with the immersion objective in pure water) is added, exhibiting a small peak (1) and a broad peak (2). Peak (1) at 1066 cm^{-1} could be related to the presence of the CO_3^{2-} , which may be present in the electrolyte due to the ambient air environment.^{3,4} Peak (2) can be assigned to the OH bending mode of H_2O .⁵ Very thin layers of surface hydroxides are also expected in the pure KOH electrolyte solution based on previous literature and magnetometry data and their interpretation in the main text, but it can be very difficult to resolve such layers using Raman spectroscopy.⁶ In the present case of *in situ* Raman measurements, the presence of large amount of water leads to significant background signals, which additionally hampers the detection of thin surface layers. A clear peak (3) at about 475 cm^{-1} , attributed to $\alpha\text{-Ni(OH)}_2$,⁵ is detected at OCP in the thiourea-containing solution. Upon application of the two-electrode reduction/oxidation potentials this peak vanishes/reappears, indicating a reversible formation/decomposition of an $\alpha\text{-Ni(OH)}_2$ surface layer. Another small peak at 730 cm^{-1} , labelled (4) can be assigned to the stretching vibrations of -C=S bonds of thiourea.⁷ Two-electrode potentials in both **a** and **b** roughly correspond to the potentials in the respective three-electrode configurations used in the main manuscript (Fig.1e and Fig.2e).

Figure S6. Density functional theory calculations for ferromagnetic NiH_x as described in the method section in the main text. The total spin magnetic moment per Ni atom shrinks almost linearly with growing x, while the lattice constant grows almost linearly.

Figure S7. Variation of magnetic saturation moment m_s , applied potential U , and current i as a function of time t during different potentiostatic switching programs performed on Ni films in 0.5 M KOH with thiourea by *in situ* SQUID magnetometry. **a** Switching between -0.95 V and -0.5 V with a holding time of 7 min per step for 60 cycles, with a pause at OCP after 50 cycles. This procedure was performed after two CVs and 15 potentiostatic switching cycles between -0.95 V and -0.5 V. **b** Switching between -1.2 V and 0.1 V for 25 cycles with a holding time of 2 min for each step in the first 15 cycles (with a pause at OCP after 5 cycles) and a holding time of 1 min for each step in the last 10 cycles. This procedure was performed after two CVs and two cycles of potentiostatic switching between -1.2 V and 0.1 V with a holding time of 7 min. Note that the difference in the absolute m_s values for a and b stem from different film thicknesses. The data shown in Fig. 2b and Fig. 2c in the main manuscript are acquired after the pause at OCP and are marked in a and b, respectively.

Figure S8. Voltage-induced switching between low- and high coercivity states during a routine of 1000 Red-Ox cycles for a Ni film in 0.5 M KOH + 1g/L thiourea. Hysteresis loops were recorded by *in situ* MOKE magnetometry during selected cycles. We started with a reduction potential of -0.95 V and applied more positive reduction potentials (up to -0.75 V), when gas evolution became too prominent. During each oxidation and reduction step, the voltage was applied for 5 s when no hysteresis loop was measured and for 2-5 min when a hysteresis loop was recorded. The electrochemical cell was refilled multiple times throughout the procedure. Within the short (5 s) reduction and oxidation steps, according to the discussion to Fig. 2b,c in the main manuscript, hydrogen absorption and desorption are expected to occur, while surface hydroxide reduction and re-oxidation may have just started. **a** Exemplary current I transients along with the voltage profile for some cycles. **b** Coercivity (upper panel) measured during reduction and oxidation steps along with the corresponding voltages (lower panel). **c** Hysteresis loops for the 1000th Red-Ox cycle. **d,e** Atomic force microscopy (AFM) images (20 μm x 20 μm) of **d** a freshly prepared Ni film and **e** the Ni film after the 1000th reduction and oxidation cycle from **b**. AFM image analysis provides a root mean square roughness of 8 and 11 nm for **d** and **e**, respectively. AFM was performed using a Nano Wizard II from JPK Instruments in intermittent mode.

Note S1: Influence of adsorbed surface hydrogen on the magnetic saturation moment

The amount of adsorbed H on the Ni surface of our samples can be calculated using the surface coverage of H on polycrystalline Ni⁸ of around $1.5 \cdot 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the surface area of our samples for SQUID magnetometry of 0.12 cm^2 . An additional surface area increase due to roughness, as determined from AFM in Figure S8, amounts only 1 to 3% and can be disregarded for the following estimation. For each adsorbed hydrogen atom a decrease in the magnetic saturation moment m_s of $0.71 \mu_B$ ($1 \mu_B = 9.274 \cdot 10^{-24} \text{ Am}^2$) is expected,⁹ which corresponds to the formation of a ‘magnetically dead layer‘ on the surface as surface Ni loses its moment completely. In our case, a total change in magnetic moment of about $1 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ Am}^2$ would therefore be expected for a full monolayer of adsorbed hydrogen atoms. As the Ni surface in our case is also covered with Ni hydroxides, such a full monolayer of adsorbed hydrogen seems unlikely even at strongly cathodic potentials. The magnetic moment change for an adsorbed hydrogen layer can also only account for 30% of the moment decrease in the 0.5 M KOH electrolyte solution (Fig.1c) and 15% of the moment decrease in the same electrolyte with thiourea. Therefore, we discuss this increase in the main text in terms of hydrogen absorption, which is expected to be the dominant cause of the moment decrease.

Note S2: Estimation of the Ni layer thickness using the magnetic moment change.

Assuming a moment increase Δm corresponding to the Ni hydroxide reduction, one can estimate the thickness of the newly formed metallic Ni layer d_{Ni} using:

$$d_{Ni} = \frac{\Delta m M_{Ni}}{\mu_{Ni} A \rho N_A}$$

,where M_{Ni} is the molar mass of Ni (58.7 g/mol), μ_{Ni} is the magnetic moment on a metallic Ni atom ($0.6 \mu_B = 5.56 \times 10^{-24} \text{ Am}^2$), A is the surface area of the measured sample (0.12 cm^2), ρ is the bulk density of metallic Ni (8.9 g/cm^3) and N_A is Avogadro’s constant.

This assumption includes no detectable moment from the Ni(OH)₂ layer, which is reasonable in view of its limited thickness and low paramagnetic susceptibility¹⁰. A rough estimation of the magnetic moment $m_{Ni(OH)_2}$ corresponding to a β -Ni(OH)₂ layer at our experimental field H of 5000 Oe (0.5 T) can be calculated via:

$$m_{Ni(OH)_2} = \chi_m \cdot H \cdot A \cdot d_{Ni(OH)_2} \cdot \rho_{Ni(OH)_2}$$

We used a density $\rho_{Ni(OH)_2}$ for β -Ni(OH)₂ of 3.97 g/cm^3 ,¹¹ an estimate for the hydroxide layer thickness $d_{Ni(OH)_2}$ of 5 nm and the mass susceptibility χ_m from Reference ¹⁰:

$$\chi_m = \frac{C}{T - \theta} = \frac{112 \cdot 10^{-4}}{300 - 20.5} = 4 \cdot 10^{-5} \frac{\text{emu}}{\text{g Oe}} = 4 \cdot 10^{-8} \frac{\text{Am}^2}{\text{g Oe}}$$

Using these values, we obtain $m_{Ni(OH)_2} = 4.8 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ Am}^2$, which is indeed negligible compared to the measured moment changes in the order of $5 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ Am}^2$.

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